

The plot difference of the epic "Malikayı Zuhriya"

(Princess Zuhriya)

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Annotaciya: Biz bul maqalamızda qaraqalpaqlar arasında qıssaxanlıq jolı menen tarqalgan «Malikayı Zuhriya» dástanınıń syujetlik ózgesheligi, ondaǵı waqıyalar qaraqalpaq dástanlarına tán ulıwmalıq belgilerge hám jeke ózgesheliklerge iye ekenligi, dástannıń ideyalıq mazmunı, obrazları hám kórkemlik ózgesheligi sıyaqlı máselelerdi sóz ettik.

Annotation: In this article, we studied issues such as the plot difference of the epic "Princess Zuhriya", which is widespread in Karakalpak through storytelling, the fact that the events have common features and differences typical of Karakalpak epics, the ideal content, images and artistic differences of the epic.

Аннотация: В данной статье мы изучили такие вопросы, как сюжетное отличие эпоса «Царевна Зухрия», который широко распространен у каракалпаков посредством повествования, наличие в событиях общих черт и различий, характерных для каракалпакских эпосов, идеальное содержание, образы и художественные отличия эпоса.

Gilt sózler: dástan, syujet, xarakter, waqıya, obraz.

Keywords: epic, episode, character, event, image.

Ключевые слова: эпос, сюжет, характер, событие, образ.

There is information that the term "episode" was used in literature by Carmel and Buano, representatives of the classicism movement who lived in the 17th century. They

adopted this concept from Aristotle, who used it when talking about the legendary heroes of the ancient Greeks.

Episode is taken from the French language and means "thing". An episode is a list or collection of events, events, including the actions of characters, expressed in a work of fiction. The episode is a means of revealing the character, its differences, a set of connections between characters suitable for the representation of specific events.⁵⁹

That is, the plot is the mutual relations of people, conflicts between them, sympathies and antipathies, relations between people in general - the development and unification of the history of this or that character, type.⁶⁰ In general, any artistic work is created with the participation of three universal elements (language, theme, plot). Although the plots have different forms, they are still decorated according to the plot writer's idea and the theme of the artistic work. It is not created according to the author's desire (including any event he want). Perhaps it is a special law that emerges from the direction of the characters in the work, the side of the events, on the contrary, the creation of the characters from the side of the events. The relationship between character and story should be such that the story is the key to character and, in the case of character, to understanding the significance of the story (of typical story). This key should reveal the importance of the main idea, the content of the event. From this point of view, plot is a sequence of events that reveal character. Regarding this, Izzat Sultan: "The characters represented in the artistic work prepare all the big and small moments of the plot, the statements and, in turn, the narratives chosen from life or created by the writer, the character is fully and clearly visible to the reader's eyes. If an artistic work is the art of creating a character and recognizing a person, then matching each large and small element of the plot to the direction of the characters is one of the artistic levels of the work. He said that any character gets the power and energy in its actions from the historical-public flow, historical-concrete conditions move them."⁶¹ We cannot say that

⁵⁹Járimbetov Q. Ádebiyattanıwdan sabaqlar. Nókis, «Qaraqalpaqstan», 2012, 23-bet.

⁶⁰ Умуров Ҳ. Адабиёт назарияси. Тошкент, «Шарқ», 2002, 129-бет.

⁶¹ И. Султон. Адабиёт назарияси. Тошкент, «Ўқитувчи», 1986. 179-бет.

this definition applies only to works created in written literature or to one type of literature. In our opinion, this idea also applies to epics, which are the basis of works of art. It is appropriate to use the achievements of the modern science of literary studies when we study the plot differences of the epics.

If we look at the comments given to the plot above, the events in the saga “Princess Zuhriya”⁶² that we are studying are given as follows. Taking into account that the copy of the epic sent to the press is not complete, and after getting acquainted with the content of the epic, we divided its plot direction into two large sections. The first is the events before Zuhria's birth and having a child, and the second is the birth and adulthood period of Zuhria's child Shakhalam, and the events related to her marriage. The plot of the first part is as follows. King Malik Qaytus lived in the city called Zulmat. One day he received a sound from the Prophet and told him that he should become a Muslim. He asks for a son for this. He says he will accept your religion after that. After nine months, the king has a daughter and does not convert to Islam. The born girl was named Malikay Zuhriya and she became a religiously literate Muslim girl supported by the prophets. The king became angry and a conflict arose between the infidel king and the Muslims. The father orders the newborn girl to be taken to the desert. There, a woodcutter found an old girl and took care of her until she was 14 years old. Then he brings him to his father. Accept him as a child, at least let him serve you, says the old man. After seeing this girl, the unbelieving old man hangs on to his daughter, saying, "You have fun with me." After not listening to what her father told her, she has thrown into the dungeon. After 40 days, he takes her out and bring her to him again, thinking that she will agree. The king hates the girl who begged the prophets for help and angrily cuts off both her hands at the wrists. Then, again, he takes the girl to the desert. The princess, who is crying hard, is sheltering in a forest on the bank of the river Joyhun. Meanwhile, Hasenkhan, the king of Khorezm, who was hunting, saw the princess and

⁶² Қарақалпақ фольклоры. Көп томлық. 63-том, «Малийкайи Зухриййа», Нөкис, «ИЛИМ», 2013.

wanted to talk to her, and when he sent someone to her, she did not want to go out. During the attack with his army, the girl was supported by God and the enemy retreated.

After returning to his palace, Hasenhan tells his mother Arkana about what happened. Arkana goes to Zuhria as a suitor. Zuhriya agreed and asked him to build a castle in his place and name it Gulistan. Hasenkhan agreed to this and built a castle and named it Gulistan. Here he married Zuhriya and had a child. Hasenkhan's elder woman hates Zuhriya, whom she deceives when the king goes to war, sends a letter to Mother Arkana on behalf of the king, and banishes her to the deserts. While trying to drink water, her child Shakhalam falls into the water. The wind helps him get out of the water. After the king returns from the war, he finds his child and Zuhriya and returns to the castle. The events of the first part of the saga end with these events, and the next events related to the life of Shakhalam begin. The events of the second part begin with the events related to Shakhalam's coming of age and departure from his parents to the land of his grandfather Malik Qaytus. Shakhalam, who aims to take revenge on his grandmother for the sufferings of his mother, asks his parents for permission. He leaves with his young men saying that I will convert the country to the Muslim religion. But when Hasenhannan is about to be defeated, help comes, he overcomes together and takes his grandmother to his mother, asks for forgiveness, and then kills her. After some time, Shakhalam goes hunting with his companions and has a dream while lying down. Sonajan, the daughter of Ziywar Shah, enters the dream and Shakhalam falls in love with her. At this time, Sona also dreams and falls in love with Shakhalam. Both of them interpret their dreams to their clerics. After knowing who each other is, Sona can't stand it and sends her concubine Ziyba to fetch Shakhalam. Resting, Ziyba takes the concubine Shakhalam to Sona. Shakhalam, who sent a letter to his parents, is having fun with Sona. When Sona's father finds out about the boy, Sona turns the prince into a parrot and hides him. Then, one day, he saw him and threw him in the dungeon. Sona can't do anything. After some time, this kingdom will be invaded by enemies, and Ziywarshah will not be able to stop them. While looking for a way to get rid of the enemy by casting lots to their friends, they say that only Shahalam, who is in the dungeon, can save them. He will be taken out of the dungeon, well fed and equipped with weapons. In the fight against the enemy,

Shakhalam wins and marries the king's daughter Sona. He returns to his country of Khorezm, the city of Gulistan, and lives happily with his parents. The plot content of the second part consists of the following.

The plot difference of the epic is that it is divided into two sections containing different content. The second part is created similar to the plot of love epics. Examples of this section include the motif of falling in love in a dream, and the motif of saving a girl's country from external enemies.

At the same time, there are many mobile plots and motifs, such as the worship of the gods of heroes, the child of a hero or a king who goes to war does not recognize his father, the birth of the child will be supported by the gods or will be miraculously born, lying in the dungeon for the girl, defending his country from foreign enemies, a shepherd or woodcutter finding a child left in the field, being brought to his parents upon reaching adulthood as in other epics of various contents in the epic.

Based on these differences, we can say that the plot of the epic has a rich and complex plot.

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